

UNVEILING THE ORAL-GUT MICROBIOME AXIS: IMPLICATIONS FOR HEALTH AND DISEASE

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Abstract. *The gut and oral microbiomes are central to health, influencing systemic functions and driving disease processes. Gut bacteria not only assist in digestion but also support essential physiological functions. Disruptions to this balance, such as from antibiotics or illness, can lead to dysbiosis, which is linked to various conditions including obesity, neurodegenerative diseases, and cancer. Similarly, the oral microbiome, influenced by factors like diet, age, and hygiene, plays a role in dental diseases and systemic conditions such as cardiovascular disease and diabetes. The emerging discovery of the oral-gut axis underscores the intricate connection between these microbiomes, revealing that oral bacteria can influence gut health and metabolism. Despite these advances, the complexity of microbiome presents therapeutic challenges. Molecular techniques, including RT-PCR, whole-genome sequencing, and deep sequencing, are enhancing diagnostic capabilities and deepening our understanding of microbial ecosystems, laying the groundwork for future breakthroughs.*

Keywords: *gut microbiome, Oral-gut axis, Molecular techniques.*

INTRODUCTION

The "microbiome" encompasses the entire genetic blueprint of microorganisms residing in different parts of the human body, acting as a secondary genome that profoundly shapes our health and physiology [1]. This secondary genome forms a symbiotic relationship with its host, exerting powerful effects on health—whether by promoting well-being, triggering disease, or remaining neutral [2]. Microorganisms thrive in environments suited to their growth, colonizing various external and internal parts of the human body, such as the skin, eyes, under the nails, and through pathways like the respiratory, gastrointestinal, and urogenital tracts, or through breaks in the skin [3]. The human microbiome composition is uniquely tailored to each individual and constantly shifts in response to factors such as age, diet, genetics, and medication, making it highly dynamic and personalized [4]. Specific microbiome profiles have been directly associated with various diseases by analyzing the differences between patients and healthy individuals, highlighting their role in disease development [5]. The gut microbiome, comprising bacteria, fungi, protozoa, and viruses in the digestive tract, plays a critical role in digestion, nutrition, detoxification, and immune system maturation [6]. Over millennia, it has co-evolved with its human host, making it a vital contributor to overall health. Intriguingly, blood plasma has revealed live microbiota and microbial

RNA in circulation, highlighting the profound impact of gut microbiome on systemic health and offering new perspectives on disease processes [7].

Figure- This diagram illustrates the intricate interplay between the gut and oral microbiomes and their profound impact on systemic health, underscoring their critical roles in a range of diseases and highlighting the potential for personalized therapeutic interventions.

The oral microbiome, second in abundance to the gut, is associated with dental diseases such as caries and periodontal disease, which are among the most prevalent conditions worldwide [8]. Dysbiosis of the oral microbiome has been linked to autoimmune diseases like primary Sjogren's syndrome (SS), systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), and rheumatoid arthritis (RA) [9]. In RA, bacteria like *Porphyromonas gingivalis* contribute by producing enzymes that trigger RA-specific antibodies [10]. Extensive characterization of oral microbiota in healthy individuals is crucial for understanding its role in disease onset [11]. Periodontal disease, one of the most common oral diseases globally, is characterized by inflammation that extends into the supporting tissues of the teeth, causing loss of attachment and bone [12]. Historically, analysis of the human oral microbiota was limited by culture-based methods, which failed to grow many microbial species due to low bacterial concentrations and the challenge of mimicking the oral environment [13]. However, metagenomics has transformed the field by allowing for the direct study of microbial community DNA, uncovering diverse unculturable flora [14]. Emerging strategies like microbial transplantation hold promise for manipulating the gut microbiome to manage or prevent diseases [15]. While the potential is significant, more well-designed studies are needed to fully understand the therapeutic benefits and long-term outcomes of microbiome modulation.

CONCLUSION-

The human microbiome, especially in the gut and mouth, is essential for health and deeply involved in diseases like obesity, neurodegeneration, cancer, and cardiovascular disorders. The oral-gut axis highlights the interplay between these microbiomes, where disruptions in one affect the other. Advances in molecular techniques, such as metagenomics and sequencing, have revolutionized our understanding, revealing new diagnostic and therapeutic potentials. Despite these breakthroughs, microbiome-targeted therapies remain underdeveloped, requiring further research to harness their full potential in disease prevention and treatment, ultimately reshaping modern medicine.

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